

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ADMINISTRATION WITHIN A SMALL-SCALE ENTERPRISE

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Key words: scope, profound influence, fundamental grasp, fabric, contemporary, Inherent assumptions, significantly impact, audience, heightened customer interest,

Annotiation; *Social media marketing has become a crucial part of every business strategy in recent years. It is especially important for small businesses that are looking to grow and expand their customer base. Social media marketing is a cost-effective way for small businesses to reach their target audience and build brand awareness. In this article, we will discuss the importance of social media marketing for small businesses and how it can help them achieve their goals.*

Introduction:

This chapter offers a succinct outline of the study presented in this thesis. It introduces the reader to the study's scope, problem statement, research's significance, and research question, alongside assumptions, limitations, and delimitations of the research. This overview sets the stage for chapter 2: the literature review.

1.1. Background:

Social media plays a pivotal role in marketing and fostering customer relationships. Small businesses are increasingly leveraging social media as a marketing tool due to its low entry barriers. However, many struggle without a

strategic approach. Consequently, without a fundamental grasp of the benefits of social media and how to utilize it for customer engagement, numerous opportunities are missed. This research seeks to initially understand how a small business, known for using social media to expand, employs it to engage customers.

1.2. Significance:

This research aims to pinpoint strategies aiding small-to-medium enterprises (SMEs) in leveraging social media to engage consumers. SMEs significantly impact the U.S. economy, constituting 99.7% of all employer firms (Small Business Administration (SBA), 2011). Understanding how small businesses utilize marketing techniques and social media to nurture business-to-consumer relationships is crucial. Although SMEs grapple with social media usage, its cost-effectiveness offers diverse marketing opportunities, crucial for enterprises constrained by limited resources.

1.3. Statement of Purpose:

This project primarily aims to identify strategies aiding SMEs in using social media to connect with consumers—a rare fusion of discussions on SME marketing strategy and social media. Most literature on social media strategy primarily studies large organizations. However, these strategies might not seamlessly apply to small businesses. This study scrutinizes a small business known for social media success, offering insights into its consumer engagement tactics. It also presents techniques and lessons that might benefit others.

1.4. Research Question:

The research endeavors to answer: "How does a small business, known for using social media to foster business growth, employ social media to engage consumers?"

1.5. Assumptions:

c within this study include the participant's use of social media for interaction,

honesty in responses, maximal effort in answering, and abstention from unclear responses.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Awareness. (2011). 11 strategies to increase engagement. Retrieved March 2, 2012, from <http://info.awarenessnetworks.com/Strategies-to-IncreaseEngagement.html> Bandee. (2012).
2. About Us. Retrieved March 2, 2012, from <http://www.thebandee.com/About.html> Berg, B.L. (2007).
3. Qualitative research methods for the social sciences (6th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson and Allyn and Bacon. Berthon, P., Ewing, M. T., & Napoli, J. (2008).
4. Brand management in small to medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 46(1), 27-45. doi:10.1111/j.1540-627X.2007.00229.x Boyatzis, R. (1998).
5. Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development. SAGE. Bresciani, S., & Eppler, M. J. (2010).
6. Brand new ventures? Insights on start-ups' branding practices. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 19(5), 356- 366. doi:10.1108/10610421011068595 Business.com. (2010, September 21).
7. How B2B marketers are finding success integrating social media & search marketing. Retrieved September 8, 2011 from <http://www.business.com/info/socialmedia-search-integration> Cohen, J. (2012, April 13). Supply your team with content to share on social media channels. Retrieved April 22, 2012, from <http://www.radian6.com/blog/tag/8020-rule/> Cordle, I. (2011, September 16).

8. Social media helps startups thrive. Miami Herald. Retrieved from http://www.miamiherald.com/2011/09/16/vfullstory/2410849_social-media-helps-startups-thrive.html Coviello, N., Brodie, R.,& Munro, H. (2000).
9. An investigation of marketing practice by firm size. Journal of Business Venturing,15(5), 523-545.